

UTTARAKHAND TOURISM: A VEHICLE FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT BY GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT CONTRIBUTION

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Abstract

Tourism is said to be the largest source of employment and entrepreneurship, both directly and indirectly. Its volume of contribution to the Gross Domestic Product for any state makes a significant impact on the overall economic development of the said state. This paper is a discussion and deliberation on these aspects of the tourism in the state of Uttarakhand of India. This state is endowed with the scenic beauty of the Himalayas and the rivers originated from it. Uttarakhand is home to a number of spiritual sites, holy rivers, iconic temples, and hill stations. The present study has been conducted through the usage of regression statistics together with ANOVA and t-Test analysis. The impact of corona pandemic on the domestic and international tourist arrivals in Uttarakhand are the main factors behind the sudden drop of tourist arrivals to the state which used to make significant contribution to the GDP of the state. The study reveals that there is a significant relation between the tourist arrivals and its impact the GDP of Uttarakhand. There are also many challenges before this sector. Therefore, the government should implement proper policies for sustainable development of the tourism sector in the state.

Keywords: Economic Development. Gross Domestic Product, Tourism, and Tourism Dimensions.

Introduction

Tourism is an economic, cultural and social phenomenon where people move from their resident for business or personal purposes. Tourism has many dimensions, like, niche tourism, experiential tourism, ecotourism, heritage tourism, agricultural tourism, and religious tourism (Thakur et. al., 2018). Niche tourism focuses on a specific concept or topic, such as, sports, wildlife, war, food, etc. Wildlife safaris in Africa is the example of such tourism. Sustainable tourism is associated with the environment. It maintains ecological environment and biodiversity with the cultural dignity of the people (Sharma, 2015). Ecotourism help educate the travellers, conserve fund and directly benefit the local economy. Medical tourism is associate with the medical facilities and its expenditure. People move to places where medial cost is affordable to them. Experiential tourism is connected with the culture, people, food, and history of any place. Religious tourism is associated with the faith and belief (Sharma & Aggarwal, 2018).

Tourism industry is connected with the global economy. Such industry has multiple stakeholders. Political, social, economic, and environmental gains are important part of the industry (Kumar, 2018). It plays a vital role for the economic development of any place. It increases work opportunity for the local communities. It helps in increasing the educational values among the peoples (Kumar & Sharma, 2022). It also increases the scope of escapism. Expenditure on tourism sector development generates income for the government. It increases the foreign exchange earnings of the government (Kumar, 2013). Direct income and indirect income are generated from tourism and travel industry. Direct income is generated by imposing taxes on income created by tourism business and employment. Indirect income is generated by supplying goods and services to the tourists (Raina et. al, 2017).

Tourism increases social bond among the peoples. Exchange of knowledge, and information leads to new understanding among them. Local people often gain new sewage systems, bus services, new roads, new playgrounds, etc. as a result of tourism (Mann, 2017). It increases community spirit as people have disposable income. It empowers women and local traders. It is considered as a key driver for recovery of any economy and helps nature by conservation of places (Raj & Kumar, 2019).

Significance of the Study

In recent years' tourism sector has seen unprecedented changes, mainly, because of technological advances, multiple start-ups, innovative accommodation models, growing interest in wellness and adventure which have transformed the sector. In the Policy 2030 Tourism Document the State Tourism envisages. Considering the tourist destinations available and the ample opportunity foreseen, the selection of the state for the study on its tourism is justified. The support and the initiatives by the government give a positive vibration that it would be very much focussed on the development as aspects of the state and contribution to the states gross domestic product simultaneously creating a niche in the world tourism map and providing a wide range of employment and entrepreneurship opportunities. In this context, the present study is significant in throwing the light upon how Uttarakhand Tourism can be visualised as a vehicle for economic development with its Gross Domestic Product Contribution.

Objectives of the Study

The study has been conducted comprising of the objectives as stated here under:

- To study the trends of tourist in pre-and post-corona pandemic period in Uttarakhand.
- To study the trend of tourist arrivals at popular destinations of Uttarakhand.
- To examine the relationship between the tourist arrivals and their contribution to the gross domestic product of Uttarakhand, and
- To throw a light upon the prospects and challenges before the Uttarakhand Tourism.

Hypotheses of the Study

Based on the objectives as defined above, the hypotheses have been formulated below:

- 1) H₀₁: There is no impact of corona pandemic on the tourist arrivals in Uttarakhand.
H_{1a}: There is impact of corona pandemic on the tourist arrivals in Uttarakhand.
- 2) H₀₂: There are no variations in the registered home stay facilities in the districts of Uttarakhand.
H_{1b}: There are variations in the registered home stay facilities in the districts of Uttarakhand.
- 3) H₀₃: There are no variations in registered home stay facilities in rural and urban areas in Uttarakhand.

H_{1c}: There are variations in the registered home stay facilities in rural and urban areas in Uttarakhand.

4) H₀₄: There is no disparity in tourist arrivals at popular destinations of Uttarakhand.

H_{1d}: There is a disparity in tourist arrivals at popular destinations of Uttarakhand.

5) H₀₅: There is no impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals at popular destinations of Uttarakhand.

H_{1e}: There is impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals at popular destinations of Uttarakhand.

6) H₀₆: There is no relationship between tourist arrivals and the gross domestic product of Uttarakhand.

H_{1f}: There is relationship between tourist arrivals and the gross domestic product of Uttarakhand.

Materials and Methods

- **Study Area Description:** Uttarakhand is a state in India with a lot of religious significance. It is divided in Garhwal and Kumaon divisions. Seven of its districts come under the Garhwal division whereas the remaining five districts come under the Kumaon division. Almora district has the highest population, followed by Dehradun, and Nainital. Rudraprayag district has the least population preceded by Champawat, and Bageshwar. It is blessed with several adventurous spots, destinations, and most revered shrines. It shares international border with China, and Nepal. It has also national border with Uttar Pradesh, and Himachal Pradesh. Dehradun is the capital of Uttarakhand. Its total geographic area is of 53,566 km², of which 65 percent is covered with forest, and 86 percent is mountainous. The northern part of the state is covered with the high Himalayan glaciers and peaks.

- Design and Approach:** This study is descriptive in design and has utilized qualitative and quantitative approaches. Secondary data for the study has been collected from various govt. reports, report of international agencies, research papers, published or unpublished thesis's, articles, etc. Based on nature and type-wise major destinations in Uttarakhand, the domestic and international tourist arrivals have been analysed. The study, further corroborates the district-wise registered units under Home Stay scheme in Uttarakhand at District-wise Popular Tourist Places in Uttarakhand. The secondary data have been collected for as between 2011-12 to 2019-20 to find out the pattern and the Relation between Gross Domestic Product and Tourist Arrivals in Uttarakhand. The study has been conducted contemporary to The Uttarakhand Tourism Development Master Plan 2007–2022 and also during the implementation of the same. These could also have thrown insights to the making of The Uttarakhand Tourism Policy 2023-30 Document too.
- Method of Analysis:** Different methods of quantitative and qualitative analysis comprising of text analysis, regression analyses, descriptive analysis, and content analysis have been performed to reveal the tourism practices in general and the future prospects in particular.

Results and Discussion

The culture and language differ in Uttarakhand. The state has beautiful landscapes surrounded with river streams, snow clad peaks, and verdant hills. Popularity of village or rural tourism is increasing day by day. Visitors can learn about the local culture and customs of the local people. Several visitors prefer to visit during 'Uttrainsi Kautik'. Delicious foods, like as Kumaoni Raita, Chainsoo, Kandalee Ka Saag, Phaanu, Baadi, Garhwal Ka Fannah, Bhang Ki Chatney, Dubuk, and Kafuli are the additional attractions (Joveriya and Mariya, 2019).

Table 1: Type-wise Major Destinations in Uttarakhand

Types	Major Destinations
Rural Tourism	Almora, Bageshwar, Chakrata, Chamoli, Deora, Pallyu, Mana. Shaukiyathal, and Tehri.
Health & Rejuvenation	Almora, Champawat, Haridwar, Jageshwar, Nainital, Ramgarh, Pithoragarh, and Rishikesh.
Sightseeing	Almora, Auli, Mussourie, Nainital, and Valley of Flowers.

Nature & Wildlife	Benog Wildlife Sanctuary, Binsar Wildlife Sanctuary, Govind Wildlife Sanctuary, Jim Corbett National Park, Kedarnath Musk Deer Sanctuary, Neel Dhara Pakshi Vihar, Nanda Devi National Park, and Rajaji National Park.
Adventure & Water sports	Auli, Dhanaulti, Jharipani, Maldevta, Shri Hemkund Sahib, Tons Valley, and Tehri Rishikesh.
Pilgrimage and Festivals	Bairnath, Badrinath, Nanda Devi, Piran Kaliyar, Jageshwar, Haridwar, Kedarnath, Rishikesh, Gangotri, and Yamunotri.

Source: Joveriya and Mariya (2019). Problems and prospects of tourism industry in Uttarakhand, *International Journal of Geography, Geology and Environment*, 1(1): 12.

Table-1 discussed the geographic and demographic profile of Uttarakhand. Uttarakhand known as "Devbhumi" is blessed with the natural beauty of Himalayas. It has diversity in flora and fauna. The native people of the state are Kumaoni, and Garhwali. Badarinarayana Temple is dedicated to Lord Vishnu. It is opened for six months in a year. The temple is mentioned in Skanda Purana, and Vishnu Purana. Kedarnath Temple is dedicated to Lord Shiva. The temple opens between the months of April and November. Nanda Devi and Valley of Flowers have been included in UNESCO World Heritage Site (Jaiswal and Bisht, 2017).

The Valley of Flowers, Hemkund Sahib, and Badrinath are situated in Chamoli district. There are a number of lakes in the state. Bhimtal, Deoria Tal, Kedar Tal, Satopanth Lake, Naini Lake, Nachiketa Tal, Dodi Tal, and Shyamla Tal are the popular lakes. Bhim Tal is surrounded with farm houses, fields, and orchards. Deoria Tal is situated near Ukhimath. Kedar Tal is situated near Gangotri. It is surrounded with skies and snow-capped mountains. Satopanth Lake has a religious significant. People believe that Brahma, Vishnu, and Mahesh have occupied each corner of the lake. Naini Lake is the largest freshwater lake and spreads over a distance of 3.5 kilometers. It is surrounded with forests, tall mountains, and rocks. Naina Devi temple is situated on its shore, is one the of 51 Shakti Peeths of India. Nachiketa Tal is situated in Uttarkashi, and is absolutely stunned with its scenery. Dodi Tal is also located in Uttarkashi. It is near the Asi Ganga that merges into the Bhagirathi near Gangotri. Shyamla Tal is spread over a nearly 1.5 square kilometre (Negi,2019).

Uttarakhand has many hidden spiritual caves. They are both man-made and natural caves. These caves are known as the jewels for tourism, and have the potentially to attract tourist. Budher Caves, Eco Cave Gardens, Ganesha Cave, Gauri Udiyar Cave, Gorcha Caves, Guchhu Pani/ Robbers Cave, Mahavatar Babaji Cave, Patal Bhuvaneshwar, Patal Rudreshwar, Timmersain Mahadev, Vashistha Cave, and Vyas Cave are the popular caves. Patal Bhuvaneshwar Cave is situated in Pithoragarh District of the Kumaon Region. It is 160-meter-

long and 90 feet deep. Lakhudiyar Cave is located in Barechhina Village of Almora District. Vyas Cave is located in Chamoli district, and situated near the famous Badrinath shrine. Robber Cave is located near Anarwala Village, Dehradun. Rai cave situated in Pithoragarh, has a Shiva temple inside it. Jhilmil cave is situated in Rishikesh. Many of the caves on the state have spiritual beliefs.

Table 2: Domestic and International Tourist Arrivals in Uttarakhand

Year	Tourist Visits		Percentage Share		Rank	
	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign
2010	30206030	127258	4.1	0.70	7	16
2011	25946254	124653	3.05	0.64	8	17
2012	26827329	124555	2.59	0.60	8	17
2013	19941128	97683	1.74	0.49	15	17
2014	21991315	101966	1.70	0.45	16	17
2015	29496938	105882	2.06	0.45	12	20
2016	30505363	117106	1.89	0.47	13	20
2017	34359989	133725	2.08	0.50	12	19
2018	35609650	151320	1.92	0.52	12	18
2019	37585920	152273	1.62	0.48	12	19
2020	7005264	41339	1.15	0.58	13	18
2021	19434475	8532	2.87	0.81	12	15
2022	54642600	61600	3.16	0.72	-	-

Source: Prepared by authors from Reports of India Tourism Statistics (2011-2023)

Table-2 discussed the tourist arrivals in Uttarakhand. It has been found that the number of tourists are increasing constantly since 2010, with an exception in 2020 which declined due to the corona pandemic. Domestic tourist arrival was more than 3.7 crores in 2019, which dropped to only 70.05 lakhs in 2020. On the other hand, foreign tourist arrivals were 1.52 lakhs in 2019, and it was just 41.33 thousand in 2020 for the pandemic. Lockdowns, and travelling restriction due to the corona pandemic were the main factors behind the sudden drop of tourist arrivals. Therefore, *the null hypothesis-1 (H_{01}) is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted*, i.e. there was an impact of corona pandemic on the domestic and international tourist arrivals in Uttarakhand.

Uttarakhand has long mountain ranges, and amazing hill stations. Tourists can involve in many activities like as paragliding, trekking, horse riding, sky walking, valley crossing camping, café hopping, stargazing, mountain biking, golfing, fishing, rafting, bird watching,

boating in lake etc. Mussoorie, Nainital, Lansdowne, Kausani, Auli, Dehradun, Dhanaulti, Almora, Ranikhet, Abbott Mount, Bhowali, Munsiyari, Bhimtal, and Pauri are the popular hill stations. Majority of the hill stations are covered with snow from December to mid-February. Mussoorie is situated in the Garhwal Himalayan ranges. It is called as ‘Queen of Hills’. Doon Valley and Shivalik ranges can be directly viewed from the town. Lal Tibba, Sir George Everest House, Landour Clock Tour, Library Point, Gun Hills, and Kempty Falls are the popular tourist places in Mussoorie. Nainital is known as the lake city of India. It is situated in Kumaon. It is covered with beautiful blooming flowers, stunning landscapes, and majestic lakes like the Naini Lake. Naina Devi Temple, Naini Lake, Nainital Zoo, Raj Bhawan, Tiffin Top, and Hanuman Garh which are the most visited tourist places in the town. Lansdowne is situated in Pauri Garhwal district. It is also called ‘Home of the Garhwal Rifles’. Sanghralaya, Darwan Singh, and Bhullatal lake are the popular places of Lansdowne.

Kausani is a beautiful hill station situated in Bageshwar district. It is called the 'Switzerland of India'. From the town tourists can observe the spectacular panoramic view of the Himalayan peaks like Nanda Devi, Panchachuli, and Trishul. Someshwar Valley, Sumitranandan Pant Museum, Kausani Shawl Factory, and Kausani Tea Estate are the other popular places. Auli is popular for its snowy slopes, and ski resorts. It is situated in Chamoli district. Chenab, and Chattrakund are the popular man-made lake situated in Auli. Dehradun is the capital of Uttarakhand, and situated in Doon Valley. Robber's Cave, Malsi Deer Park, Mindrolling Monastery, Forest Research Institute, Khalanga War Memorial, and Tapovan are the popular places of this city. Dhanaulti is popular for the panoramic views of the lofty Himalayas. It is situated in Tehri Garhwal. Surkanda Devi temple, Dashavatar temple, Barehipani & Joranda Falls, Deogarh Fort, and Aloo Khet are the popular places of Dhanaulti.

Table 3: District-wise registered units under Home Stay scheme in Uttarakhand, 2022

District	Urban Area			Rural Area		
	Registered units	Beds	Seats	Registered units	Beds	Seats
Haridwar	12	118	59	1	6	3
Nainital	39	260	136	110	708	366
Uttarkashi	6	44	22	54	432	216
Bageshwar	1	10	5	28	180	103
Tehri Garhwal	2	16	8	103	1055	461
Pauri Garhwal	0	0	0	21	138	69

Dehradun	182	1924	924	29	254	127
Pithoragarh	0	0	0	141	773	327
Chamoli Garhwal	15	140	65	111	731	350
Udham S.Nagar	2	20	10	0	0	0
Almora	3	18	10	100	716	356
Rudraprayag	3	20	10	54	294	148
TOTAL	265	2570	1249	752	5287	2526

Source: Department of Tourism, Govt. of Uttarakhand.

Table-3 discusses the district-wise details of Home Stay facilities in Uttarakhand. It has been found that home stay facilities in the districts are not the same everywhere. Dehradun, Nainital, Chamoli Garhwal, Almora, and Tehri Garhwal have more home stay facilities than the other districts. Therefore, *null hypothesis-2 is rejected, and alternative hypothesis is accepted*. It means that there are variations in registered home stay facilities in districts of Uttarakhand. It has also been observed that the registered units, seats, and beds in the rural areas are higher than the urban areas. Dehradun has the highest number of urban home-stay facilities, followed by Nainital. Home stay facilities are absent in the urban areas of Pithoragarh, and Pauri Garhwal districts. The registered home stay units, seats, and beds in urban areas are 265, 1249, and 2570, and in rural areas these are 752, 2526, and 5287 respectively. Therefore, there are variations in registered home stay facilities in rural and urban areas in Uttarakhand. So, *null hypothesis-3 is rejected, and alternative hypothesis is accepted*

The city of Almora is situated in the southern edge of the Kumaon Hills of the Himalaya range in Almora district. Jageshwar, Zero Point, Bright End Corner, Chitai Golu Devta Temple, Kasar Devi Temple, and Nanda Devi Temple are some of the other popular places of the city which is situated 1,642 meters above sea-level. Ranikhet is situated in Almora district. It is famous for its apple orchards, and natural beauty. It is situated 1,869 meters above sea level. Dunagiri Temple, Haidakhan Temple, Upat Kalika Temple, Jhula Devi Temple, Bhula Dam, and Upat Golf Course are the popular tourist attractions of the town. Abbott Mount hills-station is situated in Champawat district. It is around 1,981 m above sea level. Lohaghat, Advait Ashram, Mukri Kothri, and Abbott Mount Church are the other popular tourist attractions of the town. Bhowali is a natural paradise for tourists and located in Nainital district. It is situated 1,654 meters above the sea level. Prachin, Shyamkhet Tea Garden, Dorothy's Seat, and Jabar Mahadev Shiv Temple are some of the other popular places of it.

Munsiyari situated in Pithoragarh district, called as 'Little Kashmir' is situated 2,200 meters above the sea level. Thamari Kund, Khaliya Top, Kalamuni Top, and Birthi Falls are

the other popular places. Bhimtal is known for its pristine lakes. It is situated in Nainital district is 1,370 meters above the sea level. Hanuman Garhi, Aquarium on Bhimtal Island, and Bhimtal Lake are the major tourist attractions. Pauri is situated in Pauri Garhwal district. It is located 1,765 meters above sea level. It offers the scenic views of Neelkanth peaks, Trishul, Bandarpunch, Sumeru, Kedarnath, Jogin Group, and Gangotri Group. Ransi Stadium, Chaukhamba viewpoint, Kandoliya temple, Kyunkaleshwar Mahadev temple, and Nagdev Temple are the other popular places of it.

Table 4: Popular Tourist Destinations in Uttarakhand

Place	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Dehradun	1807383	2146489	2484289	2905303	593467	2867782
Rishikesh	592227	678041	662118	863886	171718	292806
Mussoore	2794108	2795973	2872025	3023839	1016337	1229808
Kedarnath	309764	471235	731991	1000021	135349	243012
Badrinath	654355	920466	1048051	1244993	155055	199409
Gangotri	285459	408738	447838	530334	23774	33771
Yamunotri	155129	392208	394445	465534	7728	33311
Haridwar	20508097	21009098	21577583	21770232	4021831	12718441
Almora	106006	112702	118342	128674	19201	38198
Raniketh	139310	146747	149895	152584	20206	54265
Pithoragarh	171851	243688	154385	209651	46332	53506
Champawat	89478	149071	188916	210713	47310	15711
Nainital	873395	918652	933657	933906	215749	326259
Kathgodam	151124	151202	151965	152965	37540	108109

Source: Department of Tourism, Govt. of Uttarakhand

Table-4 discusses the popular tourist destinations of Uttarakhand. It has been found that the largest number of tourists visit Haridwar, followed by Mussoore, and Dehradun while a few tourists visit Champawat, preceded by Kathgodam. Therefore, there is a disparity in tourist arrivals at popular destinations of Uttarakhand. *So, null hypothesis-4 is rejected, and alternative hypothesis is accepted.* It has also been observed that the number of tourist arrivals at popular destinations had declined in 2020 due to the corona pandemic. Though the tourist arrival in Dehradun in 2019 was 29.05 lakhs it dropped to 5.93 lakhs in 2020 respectively. The number of tourists in Rishikesh, and Mussoore was respectively 8.63 lakhs, and 30.23 lakhs in 2019, but was respectively 1.71 lakhs, and 10.16 lakhs in 2020. The number of tourist in Kedarnath, and Badrinath were 10 lakhs, and 12.44 lakhs in 2019, but it came down to 1.35

lakhs, and 1.55 lakhs in 2020 respectively. The same trends were observed in the other major tourist hubs of the state. Therefore, there are impacts of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals in popular destinations of Uttarakhand. *So, null hypothesis-5 is rejected, and alternative hypothesis is accepted.*

The Ganga, Yamuna, Alaknanda, Bhagirathi, Ramganga, Kali, Bhilangna, Saraswati, Gaula, Gori Ganga, Kosi, Mandakini, Nandakini, Pindari, and Saryu are the popular rivers of the state that originates from the Himalayas. As per Hindu mythology the Ganges is holiest among all the rivers of the country. It originates at Gomukh in gongotri while the Yamuna originate from the Yamuna glacier. The Alaknanda plays an important role in the formation of river Ganges. Bhagirathi river flows through the Gangotri glacier trek. Ramganga river is originate from the lower Himalayas of Garhwal while River Kali called as Mahakali river, flows through in Pithoragarh district. Bhilangna river originates from the foot of the Khatling Glacier and Gaula river originates from Sattal lakes near Paharpani. It passes through Haldwani, Kathgodam, and Shahi. Kosi river is originates at Dharpani Dhar. It passes through the towns, like Amdana, Bujan, Betal Gha, and Ramnagar and Mandakini river passes through Rudraprayag, Kedarnath, Ukhimath, and Sonprayag. Nandakini river originates from the Nanda Ghunghati glacier, and eventually merges with the holy Alaknanda. Pindari river is originates from the Pindari glaciers and crosses many tiny hamlets like Tharli, Kulsari, Bhagoli, and Nauti.

Uttarakhand is full of exquisite flora, and fauna. The Jim Corbett National Park, Rajaji National Park, Valley of Flowers National Park, Nanda Devi National Park, Gangotri National Park, and Govind Pashu Vihar National Park are the popular national parks of the state. The Jim Corbett National Park is the oldest national park and is situated in Nainital District. The Valley of Flowers National Park and the NDNP are situated in Chamoli District. The Gangotri National Park is the largest national park which is situated in the Post Taknaur Range, Uttarkashi. The Govind Pashu Vihar National Park & Sanctuary is famous for its beautiful nature and lush green zones. It is situated in Supin Range, Uttarakhand (Dangi,2018).

Table 5: District-wise Popular Tourist Places in Uttarakhand

District	Popular Places
Almora	Gairad Golu Dev Temple, Nanda Devi Mandir, Banri Devi Temple, Katarmal Sun Temple, Gana Nath Temple, Binsar Mahadev Temple, Jageshwar Dham Temples, Jhoola Devi Temple, Chitai Golu Temple, and Kasar Devi.
Bageshwar	Kanda, Kausani, and Baijnath.

Chamoli	Badrinath, Adbadri, Yogdhyan Badri Temple, Rudranath Temple, Auli, Bhavishya Badri, Gopeshwar, Hemkund Sahib, and Vasu Dhara.
Dehradun	Dehradun city, Chakrata, Mussoorie, and Rishikesh.
Haridwar	Har ki Pauri, Chandi Devi Temple, Rajaji National Park, Mansa Devi Temple, Sureshwari Devi Temple, and Piran Kaliyar.
Nainital	Naina peak, Kilbury, Bhowali, Bhimtal, Sattal, Kaichi Dham, and Naukuchiatal.
Pauri Garhwal	Kandoliya Temple, Kyunkaleshwar Temple, Nagdev Temple, Binsar Mahadev Temple, Jwalpa Devi Temple, Dhari Devi Temple, Neelkanth Mahadev Temple, Shri Koteswar Mahadev Temple, and Tarkeshwar Mahadev Temple.
Pithoragarh	Aadi Kailashis, Om Parvat, Chandak, Patal Bhuvaneshwar, Jhulaghat, Narayan Ashram, Thal Kedar, and Naini Saini Airport.
Rudra Prayag	Ukhimath, Chopta, and Guptkashi.
Tehri Garhwal	Devprayag, Dhanaulti, Kunjapuri, New Tehri, and Surkanda peak.
Udam S.Nagar	Drona Sagar, Atariya temple, Chaiti Devi, Lake Paradise, and Girital.

Source: Websites of districts of Uttarakhand

Table-5 depicts the district-wise popular tourist places in Uttarakhand. It has been found that these tourist places are scattered all over in various districts of the state. Uttarakhand is renowned for its pilgrimage site, and religious environment. It is home to a people of diverse tribal communities, ethnic groups, and immigrants. The People of the state speak many languages like Kumaoni, Garhwali, Bhotia, and Hindi, celebrate several festivals like Makar Sankranti (Ghughutia), Kumaon Holi, Janopunya, Kandali, Chhipla Jaat, Ghuian Ekadashi, Khatarua, Olgia or Ghee Sankranti, Dikar Puja, Ganga Dusshera or Dasar, Batsavitri, Phool Dei, Harela, Bhitali, and Basant Panchami, Kumbh Mela is the most popular festival. People take a deep in the Ganga during this festival as it redeems them of their sin. It is a three-month lengthy festival. Basant Panchami is celebrated in the month of January/ February. Kumaon community celebrate Harela festival. This festival is also known as Bhaitauli. Nanda Devi Fair (goddesses Sunanda, and Nanda) held every year in Kichha, Bhowali, Ranikhet, Munsyari, Dandidhara, Nauti, Nainital, and Almora.

Table 6: Relation between Gross Domestic Product and Tourist Arrivals in Uttarakhand

Year	Tourist Arrivals	Gross Domestic Product*
2011-12	26070907	115,328
2012-13	26951884	131,613
2013-14	20038811	149,074
2014-15	22093281	161,439

2015-16	29602820	177,163
2016-17	30622469	195,125
2017-18	34493714	219,954
2018-19	35760970	236,768
2019-20	37738193	253,666

Source: <https://statisticstimes.com/>; Note: * in crores (INR); Note: Pre-Corona pandemic analysis.

Table: 6 (a) Summary Output

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.843181734
R Square	0.710955437
Adjusted R Square	0.669663356
Standard Error	27460.51534
Observations	9

Source: Calculated by the authors.

Table 6 (b): ANOVA Analysis

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.3E+10	1.3E+10	17.21772	0.00429819
Residual	7	5.28E+09	7.54E+08		
Total	8	1.83E+10			

Source: Calculated by the authors.

	<i>Standard</i>			
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	-11772.26114	47643.2109	-0.247092102	0.811927
Tourist Arrivals	0.006629685	0.001597736	4.149423929	0.004298

Source: Calculated by the authors.

The table 6(a) shows R Square value is 0.710955437. It means there is relationship between number of tourist and gross state domestic product in Uttarkhand. Table (6-b) shows that p value (0.0042) is lower than critical value at 5% level of significance ($p > 0.05$), therefore we will reject the null hypothesis-8. Hence, it can be concluded that there is a relationship between the tourist arrivals and the gross domestic product of Uttarakhand. Tourism sector is a growing sector in Uttarakhand. It has contributed more to the economy of the state. To discuss the future prospects and challenges before this sector of Uttarakhand, the SWOC analysis has been performed below.

Tourism sector is a growing sector in Uttarakhand. It has contributed more in the economy of the state. For discussing the future prospects and challenge of tourism sector of Uttarakhand, we have done the SWOC analysis.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Potential to attract tourist inflow ➤ Tourist hill- stations ➤ Salubrious and pollution free environment ➤ Rich history and heritage ➤ Politically and socially stable state ➤ Hospitable people ➤ Scenic beauty of the nature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Geographical isolation ➤ Inadequacy of marketing ➤ Lack of transport facilities ➤ Lack of adequate infrastructural support ➤ Lack of trained tourist guides ➤ Inadequacy of information channels ➤ Inaccessible, especially in winter
Opportunities	Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Unexplored regions ➤ Eco- tourism is gaining popularity ➤ Adventure sports and trekking. ➤ Increased disposable incomes of people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Environmental factors ➤ Balancing culture & religious issues ➤ Safety & security of visitors ➤ Extreme weather conditions ➤ Accommodation & means of Transport for all strata of tourist at all weather conditions

Limitations of the Study

Any study cannot be taken as complete and perfect in all aspects as there will be limitations while actually undertaking that study. The current study is not an exception as it has the following limitations.

- The study is confined to the newly formed 27th State of India which was a part of present Uttar Pradesh.
- The Period of the study is from 2011-12 to 2019-20 and the pattern in many no way be prospective for the years to come or may not be effects from the prior study years.
- The secondary data have been taken as available from the sources cited. There may have been misrepresentation or inadequate compilation of the data at the sources itself. Further certain data have not been available too.

- There might be some places of tourist interest left unnoticed because of unknown reasons.
- Due to the unavailability of proper transport or infrastructure or even accommodation facilities the study or the data might have got affected.

Scope for Further Study

During the study and at the time of discussion, the authors have felt that the study can also throw light on the future dimensions to take the study further for better results. Some of the recommended scopes for further studies are outlined hereunder:

- The study is confined to Uttarakhand state only. It can be extended to other states in these lines as well.
- Further, the duration of the study can be increased to have better insights.
- The sources of data other than the one used for the secondary sources can be more explored.
- Other places of interest if any left unnoticed can be traced out and efforts can be made to study to bring to limelight.
- A comparative study can be made about the various aspects undivided Uttar Pradesh and the newly formed Uttarakhand State.
- A study can also be conducted on the problems and prospectus of digital access to the state.
- An interim performance review study can be made based on the State Tourism Visionary Policy Document 2030.
- An assessment study can also be done about the accomplishment of the Uttarakhand Tourism Development Master Plan 2007–2022 after the completion of the defined time period and before the implementation of the Uttarakhand Tourism Policy 2023-30 documents.

Conclusion

Uttarakhand has ample opportunities to grow and contribute substantially to the bottom line of the Gross Domestic Product of the state. Some of the dimensions of tourism like spiritual tourism proximity is of the unique nature because of its close proximity to the Himalayan Mountain Ranges because of their close to Hindu myth and religion. Locations like Dehradun, Nainital, Chamoli Garhwal, Almora, and Tehri Garhwal have more home stay facilities than

the other districts. Uttarakhand is renowned for pilgrimage site, and religious environment. It is a home to diverse tribal communities, ethnic groups, and immigrants. The impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals at popular destinations if the state was quite immense. However, it puts a lot of challenges before the state to move forward. Some of the prominent illustrative challenges before the sector can be the environmental factors, balancing culture and religious issues, facilities being provided by other states, the safety & security of visitor's extreme weather conditions, available and affordable accommodation & means of transport for all strata of tourists in all weather conditions, fair implementation of government Ppolices. Additionally, if the international tourists are taken care of then, it would also contribute significantly to the earning of the Foreign Exchanges simultaneously contributing to the Gross Domestic Product of the nation at large.

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